

Online Learning Experiences and Satisfaction of Undergraduates in San Isidro College

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ABSTRACT

Educational institutions operating during the COVID-19 pandemic are openly using the online learning modality. The online learning environment offers students sustainable learning while staying in their own homes. This learning modality helps teachers in educating students who are studying under them. However, online learning presented problems for both students and teachers, hence affecting the quality of learning and instructions. These problems include technical issues, connection problems, and access to learning materials. The study adopted the design theory of technology-based student-centered learning as an initial foundation to explore elements of the online student-centered learning environment. The study utilized a mixed method research design employing the parsimonious embedded design. San Isidro College served as the research locale and the college students enrolled during the first semester of the academic year 2021-2022 served as the respondents of the study. The quantitative data was treated using mean and ANOVA and the qualitative data were thematically analyzed. The study discovered that the students were satisfied on all eight factors: learning device, online discussion, online learning, learning community, instructors' characteristics, dialogue between instructor and students, timeliness of feedback, and effectiveness of feedback. Among the eight factors, the timeliness of feedback showed that the students were most satisfied while the instructors' characteristics ranked the lowest. Overall, the learners were satisfied with their online learning experience.

Subject Area

Learning; Online Learning

Keywords: *Online learning, Online learning satisfaction, Online instruction*

INTRODUCTION

The implementation of online learning is evident in many institutions that operates during the COVID-19 pandemic. The online learning platform provides an avenue for students to continue learning at the comforts of their own home and helps instructors provide instructions to learners under them (Brooks, Grajek, Lang, 2020). Online learning presented problems for both students and teachers affecting the quality of learning and instructions, like technical issues, connection problems, and access to learning materials (Moring, 2020)

In the Philippine settings, the abrupt change in instruction has heavily affected students since many are not well versed in platforms used for learning. The environment has also changed for them from actual instruction to online classrooms. Many students have a hard time learning at home or areas where they have no stable connection along with many distractions at home (Barrot, Llemares, and del Rosario, 2021; Rotas and Cahapay, 2020). The impact of the difficulties faced by the students are on their learning efficiency and commitment to the subject that they are taking (Ranadewa et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the study of Palmer and Holt (2009) discussed that learning satisfactions positively correlate with the quality of students' performance. The online instructions affected the learning satisfaction. Learner satisfaction is an essential outcome indicator among numerous measures for online learner success. Learner satisfaction is described as a students' assessment of a course or college experience, as well as the perceived value of the education acquired while enrolled in a college or university (Ke and Kwak, 2013).

The study served as a gauge to assess the satisfaction of the students in their online learning. The findings document their experiences as the learners navigate their academic journey virtually.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study adopts the design theory of technology-based student-centered learning (Hannafin and Land, 1997) as an initial foundation to explore elements of an online student-centered learning environment. The study involves measuring the student's learning satisfaction and gathering the students experience in an online learning modality.

Online learning satisfaction is defined as complex and multidimensional which includes varied factors such as communication, participation of students on online discussions, knowledge and support of technology, the flexibility of the workload of instructors and students, the pedagogical skill of instructors, and the feedback provided to students (Öztürk, Karamte, and Çetin, 2020; Wei and Chou, 2020).

Figure 1

Schematic diagram of the conceptual framework of the study

The theoretical framework of the study as shown in Figure 1 illustrates the parsimonious embedded design. The independent variable is the students online learning experience where the eight factors of satisfaction is embedded to quantitatively measure the students' online learning satisfaction. The students' experience along with the numerical data assessed the students online learning satisfaction.

The factor on *Learning Devices* assesses the students experience with the technical aspect of learning. The factor on *Online Discussion* evaluates the students experience in online classes and discussion. The factor on *Online Learning* checks the students point-of-view in online learning. The factor on *Learning Community* evaluates the students' perception and experience in their online classroom and their classmates. The factor on *Instructors' Characteristics* assesses the students' perception on their instructors. The factor on *Dialogue between Instructor and Students* evaluates the experience between the relationship of the instructor and the students. The factor on *Timeliness of Feedback* checks whether the feedback from the instructors reached the students in an appropriate time. And, the factor on *Effective Feedback* measures whether the feedback provided by the instructor has an impact on the students or whether the students has received and processed the feedback given to their performance.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study assessed the satisfaction of the undergraduate students in online learning during the first semester of the academic year 2021-2022. The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the satisfaction and experience of the undergraduate students in terms of;
 - a. learning device;
 - b. online discussion;
 - c. online learning;
 - d. learning community;
 - e. instructors' characteristics;

- f. dialogue between instructor and students;
 - g. timeliness of feedback; and
 - h. effectiveness of feedback?
2. Is there a significant difference between the eight factors of online learning satisfaction?

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study utilized a mixed method research design employing the parsimonious embedded design. The study has a heavy reliance on the quantitative data where the qualitative data will supplement the quantitative data. The study used the simple random sampling in gathering the data. San Isidro College served as the research locale where in online instruction were employed during the pandemic. The participants of the study were the college students enrolled for the first semester of the Academic Year 2021-2022. Data were gathered from all of the schools in the college. There were 733 students enrolled during the first semester and the researchers gathered 269 random samples from the nine different schools.

The major instrument adapted for the study is the questionnaire developed by Davis (2014) containing eight (8) major factors in online learning satisfaction, namely: *Learning Devices* with 3 statements reflecting the students' experience with their learning equipment. *Online Discussion* with 3 statements reflecting the students' experience in online classes. *Online Learning* with 3 statements reflecting the students' insights in online classes. *Learning Community* with 3 statements reflecting the students' experience in the online classroom and their peers. *Instructors Characteristics* with 3 statements reflecting the instructors' ability in the class and instructions. *Dialogue between Instructor and Students* with 3 statements reflecting the interaction between student and teacher. *Timeliness of Feedback* with 3 statements reflecting the aptness of the instructors' feedback. And *Effectiveness of Feedback* with 3 statements reflecting the impact of the feedback given by the instructors towards the learners' performance.

The questionnaire provided a space for a short narrative comment from the students on their experience in each of the eight factors. A 5-point Likert scale evaluates the students online learning satisfaction. The questionnaire has a Cronbach-alpha of 0.736. The questionnaire asked for feedback about the students' experiences during online learning based on the eight factors of satisfaction. The criteria used the following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
5	4.21–5.00	<i>Very Satisfied</i>
4	3.41–4.20	<i>Satisfied</i>
3	2.61–3.40	<i>Neither</i>
2	1.81 – 2.60	<i>Unsatisfied</i>
1	1.00 – 1.80	<i>Very Unsatisfied</i>

The quantitative data employed the ANOVA test to compare the eight factors and the used assessed the satisfaction of the students in online learning. The qualitative data were treated using thematic analysis to categorize the students answers into a common theme. The qualitative result supported the quantitative results to strengthen the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Eight Factors of Online Learning Satisfaction

Table 1 presents the mean score with qualitative interpretation on the eight factors of online learning satisfaction and presents the degree of satisfaction of the students.

Table 1
Online learning satisfaction of the undergraduate students

FACTORS	MEAN	Q.I.	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
Timeliness of Feedback	3.82 a	Satisfied		
Online Discussion	3.75 ab	Satisfied		
Learning Community	3.63 abc	Satisfied		
Effectiveness of Feedback	3.59 bc	Satisfied	4.562	0.000**
Learning Devices	3.58 bc	Satisfied		
Dialogue between Instructor and Student	3.55 bc	Satisfied		
Online Experience	3.54 bc	Satisfied		
Instructors Characteristics	3.52 c	Satisfied		
OVERALL	3.62	Satisfied		

NOTE: ** – Significant at 0.01

As shown in Table 1, the students have expressed that they are satisfied in each parameter on online learning satisfaction. It follows that, generally, the learners were satisfied with their experience in online learning. Table 1 also shows that there is a significant difference between the eight parameters. Hence, Table 1 shows that the timeliness of feedback is the parameter that the students were most satisfied and instructors' characteristics is the parameter that the students have the lowest satisfaction rate.

Timeliness of feedback, with the highest rating, could be attributed to the students' desire to know their performance in the different activities that they submitted. Additionally, the information provided by the instructor could help the student improve themselves and work on their weak point (Pasani, Amelia, and Hassanhassan, 2020). On the other hand, the instructors' characteristics, with the lowest rating, can be attributed to the lack of physical presence of the instructor. The students are not familiar with their instructors and they have not mingled with them physically. Student are not assured of the characteristics of their instructor if what they perceived online would be similar to the actual characteristics (Brooks, Grajekm and Lang, 2020; Wei and Chou, 2020).

Online learning is not easy, especially for students who are not ready and equip with the needed resources for online learning. However, students adapt in order to comply and continue with their learning (Taja-on, Miras, and Jurolan, 2021; Wei and Chou, 2020). The students' learning satisfaction is not just a one-sided endeavor, but the students, teachers, and even parents contribute to the success of online learning (Brooks, Grajekm and Lang, 2020; Davis, 2014). Students and teachers faced challenges in the implementation of online learning and necessary adjustments were done in order to succeed. The result of the study establishes that students are satisfied with their online learning experience (Basar, Mansor, Jamaludin, and Alias, 2021; Pasani, Amelia, and Hassanhassan, 2020)

Online Learning Satisfaction Under Learning Device of Undergraduates

Table 2 shows the mean score with qualitative interpretation in satisfaction to online learning concerning learning devices. The table presents the degree of satisfaction of the students' regarding the use of learning device.

Table 2
Students' satisfaction on the use of learning device

FACTORS	MEAN	QUALIFYING INTERPRETATION
Authenticity of communication	3.78	Satisfied
Meaningful relationship	3.49	Satisfied
Presence of Instructor	3.47	Satisfied
OVERALL	3.58	Satisfied

As shown in Table 1, the students were satisfied in their overall use of learning device. Moreover, as shown in Table 2, the learners are satisfied in all statements under the use of learning devices. Students are well versed in using their devices and are familiar with the technical applications. Learning devices have helped students process information and supplement their learning (Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020; Bower et al., 2015). Additionally, learning devices are crucial for the implementation of online learning and can help students establish relationship between their classmate with the guidance of their instructors (Ranadewa et al., 2021; Yra et al., 2020; Marra, Moore, and Kilmczak, 2004).

Figure 2 displays the overview of the experiences of the students on the use of learning devices and the percentage of the main themes. The major themes were recorded: online learning and resources (28.25%), positive experience (8.92%), online challenges (6.69%), deficiency and availability of equipment (46.10%), manipulating and using equipment (5.95%). Several students (4.46%) gave no response. For every theme, sub themes were also recorded. Through these responses, the researchers have a baseline data for students' experience in using learning devices like phones and computers and the technical aspect of learning.

Figure 2
Overview of the thematic chart on the experience of the students on the use of learning device

Frame 1 listed the main themes and sub-themes of students’ experience on using learning device. Examples of the verbatim responses of the students were extracted to support the themes and sub-themes listed.

Frame 1
Summary of the qualitative themes on the experience of the students on the timeliness of feedback

Themes	Sub-themes	Example
Online Learning and Resources	Accessible	“you can access google if you don’t understand”
	Helpful	“...really helpful, online references are helpful”
	Manageable	“I am used to phones, it makes learning easier”
	Enjoyable	“Very fun and faster to learn”
Positive Experience	Comfortable	“I am comfortable learning online...”
	Convenient	“easy to upload my assignments.”

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	Makes Learning Easy	<i>“easy to use when it comes to online learning”</i>
	Relationship	<i>“easiest way of communicating with classmate and teachers”</i>
Online Challenges	Challenging	<i>“using the device for class is difficult since I am new to it”</i>
	Tiring	<i>“...virtual communication is tiring.”</i>
	Exposure	<i>“radiation sometimes is not so advisable, too much.”</i>
	Weather	<i>“Sometimes, no signal and internet due to weather.”</i>
Deficiency and Availability of Equipment	Device	<i>“...difficult because I don’t have laptop...”</i>
	Communication	<i>“needs load to be able to connect with teachers and others”</i>
	Connection	<i>“Internet connections are not very cooperative”</i>
	Quality	<i>“My device has low quality...”</i>
	Signal	<i>“difficult...because of weak signal.”</i>
Manipulating and Using Equipment	Complicated	<i>“Complicated and takes time to adjust”</i>
	Confusing	<i>“...confusing sometimes”</i>
	Expensive	<i>“...only using data...really expensive”</i>

NOTE: Responses are copied verbatim

Theme 1 and 2: *Online Learning and Resources and Positive Experience.* The first theme has four sub-themes, namely accessible, helpful, manageable, and enjoyable. The second theme has four sub-themes, namely comfortable, convenient, makes learning easy, and relations. The students expressed that the learning device has helped them in their online learning making the process easier since they are able to access sites that can assist them. Some of the students responded that the learning device made their learning manageable and enjoyable.

Learning devices can help learner access and obtain relevant information that made their learning easier (Basar, Mansor, Jamaludin, and Alias, 2021; Makel et al., 2020; Pasani, Amelia, and Hassanhassan, 2020). The availability of information to the students makes it easier for them to comply with their requirement, open sites and videos to supplement learning, and manage task with the applications available in the devices (Brooks, Grajeek, and Lang, 2020). Additionally, communication between learners and their instructors were made available during the pandemic because of the devices and application that were used in class. Building a relationship between students and making it easier for many to learn and comply online (Ranadewa et al, 2021; Wei and Chou, 2020; Blackmon and Major; 2012).

Theme 3, 4, and 5: *Online Challenges, Deficiency and Availability of Equipment, and Manipulating and Using Equipment.* The third theme has four sub-themes, namely challenging, tiring, exposure, and weather. The fourth theme has five sub-themes, namely device, communication, connection, quality, and signal. And the fifth theme has three sub-themes, namely complicated, confusing, and expensive.

The students have expressed that they have encountered problems in learning online because of the devices that they have. Some students could not afford high quality devices (i.e., high-definition screen, fast processing speed, large internal storage) as it is expensive and many has invested in load or connection to be able to participate in online discussions. Some students who

are living in remote area have expressed problems in connection as their area could not sustain a stable service and can even be affected by the weather. Few students have stated that they are not confident in using their devices and applications due to some of them being unfamiliar and find it complicated to use.

Technology inherently affects the students learning experience, especially in participating in class and submitting requirements (Barak, 2018; Henderson, Selwyn, and Aston, 2017). The challenges experienced by the students can be attributed to the technical problems that come along with the technology that they are using. Unfamiliarity to the device, unstable internet connection, and expenses to sustain online learning can contribute to the difficulties of the students (Bower, Dalgarno, Lee, and Kenney, 2015; Viotsidis et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020).

As presented in Table 2, the students were satisfied in all the parameters under the learning device, even with the use of phones or computers. This finding is supplemented in Frame 1 on the sub-theme on relation, where the learners have felt the authenticity of communication between other students and their instructors. Moreover, the learners felt the presence of their instructors since they are able to contact their instructors using the applications. Building a meaningful relationship that has helped the learners comply and submit their requirement and providing an easy way to attend online classes as shown in Frame 1. The students are satisfied with the factor of learning device.

Online Learning Satisfaction Under Online Discussion of Undergraduates

Table 3 shows the mean score with qualitative interpretation in satisfaction to online learning concerning online discussion and presents the degree of satisfaction of the students' regarding the experience with online discussion.

Table 3

Students' satisfaction in online discussion

FACTORS	MEAN	QUALIFYING INTERPRETATION
Convenience	3.94	Satisfied
Time to think and formulate a response	3.79	Satisfied
Comfortable in participating in discussion	3.52	Satisfied
OVERALL	3.75	Satisfied

As shown in Table 1, the student is satisfied in their overall experience in online discussion. Moreover, as shown in Table 3, the learners are satisfied in all statements under the experience on online discussion. Online discussions function as a supplement to the materials that the instructors provide for the learners (Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020). Conducting online classes can help the satisfaction of the students in learning as it provides them an avenue to ask the instructor directly on their concerns and feel the presence of their classmates that will help them feel less anxious (Taja-on and Miras, 2021; Zhang et al., 2020).

Figure 3 displays the overview of the experiences of the students in online discussion and the percentage of the main themes. The major themes were recorded: positive learning experience (41.64%), negative learning experience (14.87%), positive personal experience (4.83%), negative personal experience (12.64%), and technical problem (16.36%). Several students stated they have no experience (4.09%) and gave no response (5.58%). In every theme, sub themes were also

recorded. Through these responses, the researcher has a baseline data for students' experience during the online discussions that were provided in their classes.

Figure 3
 Overview of the thematic chart on the experience of the students in online discussion

Frame 2 listed the main themes and sub-themes of students' experience in online discussion. Examples of the verbatim responses of the students were extracted to support the themes and sub-themes listed.

Frame 2*Summary of the qualitative themes on the experience of the students in online discussion*

THEMES	SUB-THEMES	EXAMPLE	
Learning Experience	Flexible	<i>"It's a flexible outlet to learn in new normal."</i>	
	Helpful	<i>"Online discussion helps us learn"</i>	
	Positive	Informative	<i>"Online discussions were impormative"</i>
		Satisfied	<i>"at first it's hard but now it's okay."</i>
		Effective	<i>"I can learn more just like a traditional teaching"</i>
	Negative	Difficult for Slow Learners	<i>"Strategies and solutions are given but I am slow."</i>
		Difficulty in Understanding	<i>"Sometimes I can't clearly understand the lesson"</i>
		Harder	<i>"Hard, unlike discussing personally"</i>
		Limited Learning	<i>"I learned something but I really want to learn more"</i>
		Not Effective	<i>"Somehow ineffective in terms of learning."</i>
Personal Experience	Economical	<i>"Online classes have saved me money..."</i>	
	Positive	Fun at Times	<i>"It were fun, full of experience, and learning."</i>
		Interesting	<i>"...online classes are very interesting."</i>
		Preferred Mode of Learning	<i>"I love online class"</i>
	Negative	Anxious	<i>"sometimes I feel worry and nervous"</i>
		Challenging	<i>"... I'm not accustomed this learning"</i>
		Many Distractions at Home	<i>"Its not easy if your surrounding is so noisy"</i>
		Stressful	<i>"it is stressing despite of the efforts of everyone"</i>
	Uncomfortable	<i>"...makes me more uncomfortable"</i>	
	Technical Problems	Connection	<i>"The connectivity issues makes it hard for me."</i>
Slow or No Internet		<i>"it is hard when the Internet is slow"</i> <i>"Difficult it is because it is not stable network"</i>	
No Experience		<i>"We don't meet in online, just sending videos."</i>	

NOTE: Responses are copied verbatim

Theme 1: Learning Experience. The theme was broken in two categories regarding the positive and negative learning experience of the students. The positive experience has five sub-themes, namely flexible, helpful, informative, satisfied, and effective. Some of the students stated that online discussions have been beneficial for many of them because they act as a supplement to the materials that were provided in their online classrooms.

Online discussions are provided by instructors to cover that materials that were given to the students in their online classrooms (Taja-on, Miras, and Jurolan, 2021; Brooks, Grajeek, and Lang,

2020), Online discussions offer a flexible instruction to students the helps in gathering information and organizing their ideas, especially when the materials are confusing for them to learn alone (Basar, Mansor, Jamaludin, and Alias, 2021; Pasani, Amelia, and Hassanhassan, 2020).

The negative experience has five sub-themes, namely difficult for slow learners, difficult in understanding, harder, limited learning, and not effective. Some students have expressed that online discussion is difficult due to the online nature of learning and does not address all the types of learners. Some learners are not comfortable with learning online as they are not that confident with themselves and find it harder to understand the discussion especially when they cannot have a proper interaction with their classmates and teacher (Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020; Barak, 2018; Henderson, Selwyn, and Aston, 2017).

Theme 2: Personal Experience. The theme was broken in two categories regarding the positive and negative personal experience of the students. The positive has four sub-themes, namely economical, fun at times, interesting, and preferred mode of learning. Some of the learners found that online learning can be fun and have piked their interest making some prefer the online learning modality (Ranadewa et al, 2021; Blackmon and Major; 2012).

The negative has five sub-themes, namely anxious, challenging, many distractions at home, stressful, and uncomfortable. Some students find online discussions challenging and stressful because of the distractions they have at home or the area where they are having their online class making them anxious and uncomfortable (Barak, 2018).

Theme 3: Technical Problem. The theme has two sub-themes, namely: connection and slow or no internet. Online learning is prone to some technical problems experienced by the students. The problems either forces the students to be absent in class or have a choppy connection making it difficult to understand the discussion (Bower, Dalgarno, Lee, and Kenney, 2015; Viotsidis et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020).

As presented in Table 3, the students were satisfied in all the parameters under the online discussion. Online discussion provides help to students to understand the materials that were provided for them in their online classroom as supplemented in Frame 2 on the sub-theme of informative and helpful. Additionally, the learners find the online discussion effective as they can communicate with their instructors when they are in class and they can also communicate with their classmates making the online discussion effective as shown in Frame 2 on the sub-theme on flexible and interesting. The students are satisfied with the factor in online discussion.

Online Learning Satisfaction Under Online Learning of Undergraduates

Table 4 shows the mean score with qualitative interpretation in satisfaction to online learning concerning to the experience to online learning and presents the degree of satisfaction of the students’ regarding the online learning experience.

Table 4. Students’ satisfaction in online learning.

FACTORS	MEAN	QUALIFYING INTERPRETATION
Enjoyable	3.81	Satisfied
Meeting personal need in learning environment	3.45	Satisfied
Preference to online learning	3.36	Neither Satisfied or Unsatisfied
OVERALL	3.54	Satisfied

As shown in Table 1, the student is satisfied in their overall online learning experience. Moreover, as shown in Table 4, the learners are satisfied in all statements under the online learning experience. Learning online can be fun and meaningful for some students, however some students find it difficult to learn and access information. Additionally, online learning has a wide range of tools that can help student in their learning, but without proper training or guidance, the tools will be confusing and difficult (Taja-on, Miras, and Jurolan, 2021; Rotas and Cahapay, 2020). Learners still prefer face-to-face learning as they are more attuned to the learning modality and feel that they can do better as compared to learning online (Morin, 2020).

Figure 4
Overview of the thematic chart on the experience of the students in online learning

Figure 4 displays the overview of the experiences of the students in online learning and the percentage of the main themes. The major themes were recorded: positive experience (53.90%),

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negative experience (13.75%), and technical experience (25.65%). Several students (6.69%) gave no response. In every theme, sub themes were also recorded. Through these responses, the researchers have a baseline data for students' experience in their personal and academic process in online learning.

Frame 3 listed the main themes and sub-themes of students' experience in online learning. Examples of the verbatim responses of the students were extracted to support the themes and sub-themes listed.

Frame 3

Summary of the qualitative themes on the experience of the students on the timeliness of feedback

THEMES	SUB-THEMES	EXAMPLE	
Positive Experience	Personal	Enjoyable	<i>"Challenging and fun at the same time."</i>
		Comfortable	<i>"online classes are comfortable to me"</i>
		Convenient	<i>"convenient during this pandemic"</i>
		Conducive	<i>"online learning is confusing"</i>
	Learning	Easy Access to Information	<i>"Easy access to information..."</i>
		Efficient	<i>"I prefer it because it is time efficient"</i>
		Effective	<i>"Its good because we tackle what we need to know"</i>
		Helpful	<i>"...helps students in an effective way"</i>
Negative Experience	Personal	Uncomfortable	<i>"I feel awkward when answer if my parents are at home"</i>
		Exhausting	<i>"It is seems draining at some point."</i>
		Too Much Exposure to Radiation	<i>"...too much exposure to radiation"</i>
	Learning	Little Motivation	<i>"...simply not motivated in online class"</i>
		Lack of Interest	<i>"i dont like learning online"</i>
		Not Effective	<i>"...not that effective for learning"</i>
		Promotes Procrastination	<i>"It makes us lazy since it's just answer sheets."</i>
Technical Experience	Learning	Stressful	<i>"Very Stressful"</i>
		Joining Classes	<i>"Sometimes students cannot participate to the class"</i>
		Connection	<i>"There's a problem sometimes of connection"</i>
		Adjusting	<i>"hard to learn because we don't have devices and proper connection"</i>
		Expensive	<i>"Difficult to handle through the cost of connection"</i>

NOTE: Responses are copied verbatim

Theme 1: Positive Experience. The theme has two categories, namely the personal and learning experiences. The personal experience has four sub-themes, namely enjoyable, comfortable, convenient, and conducive. The learning experience has four sub-themes, namely easy access to information, efficient, effective, and helpful. Students expressed that online learning, during the pandemic, had helped them continue with their degree.

Though they are in the confines of their homes, they are still able to learn and develop their skills. Online learning is just as effective as traditional learning. Students during the pandemic are still able to pursue their degree and continue the learning process (Taja-on, Miras, and Jurolan, 2021; Kapur, Dwivedi, Arora, and Gandhi, 2020).

Theme 2: Negative Experience. The theme has two categories, namely the personal and learning experience. The personal experience has four sub-themes, namely uncomfortable, exhausting, too much exposure to radiation, and little motivation. The learning experience has four sub-themes, namely: lack of interest, not effective, promotes procrastination, and stressful. Students also experienced negative aspect of online learning as some of them are not that adept or interested in online learning (Basar, Mansor, Jamaludin, and Alias, 2021; Rotas and Cahapay, 2020).

Theme 3: Technical Experience. The theme has five sub-themes, namely joining classes, connection, learning, adjusting, and expensive. Technical experiences are part of the learning experience when doing online learning and students will have this experience at some point in learning (Rotas and Cahapay, 2020; Morin, 2020).

As presented in Table 4, the students were satisfied in two of the parameters and were neither satisfied nor unsatisfied in one parameter. The two parameters where the student is satisfied can be supported by Frame 3 on the sub-themes on positive personal and learning experience. Students have stated that learning online can be fun and conducive. But some students still do not prefer online learning as they find the experience difficult due to technical and connection problem, this is shown in Frame 3 on the themes of negative experience and technical experience. The students are satisfied with the factor in online learning.

Online Learning Satisfaction Under Learning Community of Undergraduates

Table 5 shows the mean score with a qualitative description in satisfaction to online learning concerning the learning community. The table also presents the degree of satisfaction of the students' regarding the learning community.

Table 5
Students' satisfaction on the learning community

FACTORS	MEAN	QUALIFYING INTERPRETATION
Easy communication with other students	3.86	Satisfied
Promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students	3.53	Satisfied
Confidence in completing work with other students	3.50	Satisfied
OVERALL	3.63	Satisfied

As shown in Table 1, the students are generally satisfied in their learning communities. Moreover, as shown in Table 5, the learners are satisfied in all statements under the learning community. Furthermore, learning communities help students learn and support each other, especially in the time of pandemic where they are not physically going to see each other (Morin, 2020). Students in online learning could not naturally interact with each other. The learning community that teachers prepare like Messenger™ or their google classrooms will provide students with avenues to interact and get to know each other (Taja-on and Miras, 2020).

Additionally, learning communities act as support communities for students who feel like they are doing it alone and help them relate to others who has the same struggle as them. Learning communities provide students also with venues to share their ideas, especially learners who are not confident in talking during online discussions (Brooks, Grajek, and Lang, 2020; Farrell and Brunton; 2020; Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020).

Figure 5 displays the overview of the experiences of the students on the learning community and the percentage of the main themes. The major themes were recorded e.g. supportive (63.57%), academic (13.38%), and negative or uncomfortable interactions (8.82%). Several students (15.94%) gave no response. For every theme, sub themes were also recorded. Through these responses, the researchers have a baseline data for students’ experience in the online learning community and the activities that the students are doing online with their peers.

Figure 5
Overview of the thematic chart on the experience of the students on the learning community

Frame 4 listed the main themes and sub-themes of students’ experience in the learning community. Examples of the verbatim responses of the students were extracted to support the themes and sub-themes listed.

Frame 4
Summary of the qualitative themes on the experience of the students on the learning community

THEMES	SUB-THEMES	EXAMPLE
Supportive	Approachable	“my classmates are approachable in terms in academic”
	Concerned	“They ask regarding my self and my performance”
	Encouraging	“it’s great and we motivate each other.”

Academic	Friendly	<i>“They are friendly and I made friends.”</i>
	Relational	<i>“even though we just meet online, we are good”</i>
	Competitive	<i>“They were really competitive”</i>
	Fun	<i>“they are very fun to talk to and goofy sometimes.”</i>
	Informative	<i>“help one another in giving information in the class”</i>
	Connected	<i>“It is solid even if we did not see each other”</i>
	Team Work	<i>“We help one another to learn more”</i>
Negative or Uncomfortable Interactions	Helpful	<i>“they help me become more confident”</i>
	Awkward	<i>“Its awkward to approach my classmates”</i>
	Selfish	<i>“They are not helpful and do not give proper information”</i>
	Unfamiliar Communication	<i>“I barely talk to them because I don’t know them.”</i> <i>“It is difficult to connect with my fellow students”</i>

NOTE: Responses are copied verbatim

Theme 1: Supportive. The theme has five sub-themes, namely approachable, concerned, encouraging, friendly, and relational. Students are naturally going to interact with one another and building a community is part of their learning experience. Students have stated that their experience with their classmates has been supportive. Students found their learning community to be friendly. They encourage one another. Student could approach each other when they want to be clarified or just wanted to connect with their peers (Taja-on and Miras, 2021; Farrell and Brunton, 2020; Roddy et al., 2017).

Theme 2: Academic. The theme has six sub-themes, namely competitive, fun, informative, connected, teamwork, and helpful. Students have not diverged from the purpose of online learning. Students still compete with each other in an online setting, but they connect with each other and try to make the learning process fun for all. Students connect with one another to gather or give information, helping each other along the way (Brooks, Grajek, and Lang, 2020; Farrell and Brunton, 2020; Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020).

Theme 3: Negative or Uncomfortable Interactions. Some students who are not active in their group chats or are not comfortable talking to their classmates may experience some uncomfortable exchanges. This may be caused by their unfamiliarity with one another and may evoke a feeling of awkwardness when they initiate a conversation (Barrot, Llanares, and del Rosario, 2021; Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020).

As presented in Table 5, the students were satisfied in all the parameters under the learning community. Learning communities provide students with an avenue to continue communicating with their classmates and exchange information from each other. Some students even motivate and support each other in the activities and classes that they have. As shown in Frame 4 under the theme of supportive and academic learners try to mitigate the distance with the online applications of communication to connect with each other. Contrarily, some students have also expressed some negative or uncomfortable interactions since some of them have never physically met each other and making the online interaction awkward. The students are satisfied with the factor in learning community.

Online Learning Satisfaction Under Instructor Characteristics of Undergraduates

Table 6 shows the mean score with qualitative interpretation in satisfaction to online learning concerning the students experience on the characteristic of the instructor and presents the degree of satisfaction of the students’ regarding the instructors’ characteristics.

Table 6
Students’ satisfaction regarding instructors’ characteristics

FACTOR	MEAN	QUALIFYING INTERPRETATION
Help with learning issues	3.67	Satisfied
Creative use of technology	3.48	Satisfied
Quality of instruction	3.42	Satisfied
OVERALL	3.52	Satisfied

As shown in Table 1, the students are satisfied with their instructor’s characteristic. Moreover, as shown in Table 6, the learners are satisfied in all statements under the students experience with the characteristics of the instructor. Instructors play a very important role in the teaching and learning process of students. Students need assistance from their instructors and clarification on some aspects of their materials (Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020). As displayed in Table 5, students were satisfied with their instructors as they have helped the learners with their concerns. The students have provided quality instructions to the learners (Taja-on, Miras, and Jurolan, 2021). Instructors who support and motivate can help the learners overcome the challenges of online learning and make the learning experience for students more meaningful (Farrell and Brunton, 2021).

Figure 6 displays the overview experiences of the students with their instructor characteristics and the percentage of the main themes. The major themes were recorded: professional (57.25%), accommodating (15.94%), willing to compromise (14.50%), and unfavorable experience (7.06%). Several students (5.95%) gave no response. For every theme, sub themes were also recorded. Through these responses, the researchers have a baseline data for students’ experiences with their instructors.

Figure 6
Overview of the thematic chart on the experience of the students regarding their instructors

Frame 5 listed the main themes and sub-themes of students’ experience regarding instructors’ characteristics. Examples of the verbatim responses of the students were extracted to support the themes and sub-themes listed.

Frame 5
Summary of the qualitative themes on the experience of the students regarding their instructors

THEMES	SUB-THEMES	EXAMPLE
Professional	Determined	<i>“I see how determined they are in teaching us.”</i>
	Efficient	<i>“they are trying their best to teach online”</i>
	Engaging	<i>“...more engaging”</i>
	Friendly	<i>“all my teachers are very friendly and good”</i>
	Good Teaching Strategy	<i>“..have the good teaching towards us students.”</i>
	Innovative	<i>“A lot of innovative approaches are being applied.”</i>
Accommodating	Addresses Issues	<i>“...addressed concerns and issues before...”</i>
	Approachable	<i>“...among mga instructor is mga approachable”</i>
	Connected	<i>“I can communicate my instructors always”</i>

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Willing to Compromise	Responsive	"...some instructors that always respond"
	Considerate	"they give a consideration to us students"
	Helpful	"Instructors have been very helpful to me"
	Motivational and Supportive	"Motivated us to learn despite of online learning"
	Patient and Sympathetic	"They are kind and extending their patience."
	Understanding	"its good to have instructor that always understand"
Unfavorable Experience	Difficult to Contact	"Instructors did not yet reply to my message"
	Internet Problems	"They have difficulty because of the internet"
	Little Interactions	"Cannot cater all the worries of the learners"

NOTE: Responses are copied verbatim

Theme 1: Professional. The theme has six sub-themes, namely determined, efficient, engaging, friendly, good teaching strategy, and innovative. The learners have seen and observed the different strategies used by their teachers to teach online classes and have found it engaging and efficient. The students have seen the determination of the teachers to deliver quality instruction (Khatry and Yousef, 2021; Kimmons, 2020).

Theme 2 and 3: Accommodating and Willing to Compromise. The second theme has four sub-themes, namely addressed issues, approachable, connected, and responsive. While the third theme has five sub-themes, namely considerate, helpful, motivational and supportive, patient and sympathetic, and understanding. Students were satisfied with the exchanges they had with their instructors. Some students stated their instructors were understanding and considerate to their reasons regarding their academic performance. Some teachers were also willing to help the students while motivating and supporting them with their learning tasks (Farrell and Brunton, 2021; Roddy et al., 2017).

Theme 4: Unfavorable Experience. The theme has three sub-themes, namely difficult to contact, internet problems, and little interaction. Around 7% of the students were not satisfied with their interaction with their instructors. Some of them were difficult to contact. Additionally, some students have encountered the difficulty due to connection problems, making it hard to properly communicate with their instructors (Barrot, Llanares, and del Rosario, 2021; Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020).

As shown in Table 6, the students were satisfied in all the parameters under the instructors' characteristics. The perception of the students towards their instructors' is crucial for learning, especially on the online setting. If students are intimidated with their instructors, the learners will have an unfavorable experience towards their learning as shown in Frame 5 under the sub-themes on difficult to contact and little interactions. But, overall, the learners are satisfied with the learning experience given by their instructors. This is shown in Frame 5 under the themes of professional, accommodating, and willing to compromise. The students are satisfied with the factor in instructors' characteristics.

Online Learning Satisfaction Under Dialogue Between Student and Teachers of Undergraduates

Table 7 shows the mean score with qualitative interpretation in satisfaction to online learning concerning the dialogue between student and teacher and presents the degree of satisfaction of the students' regarding the dialogue between students and teacher.

Table 7

Students' satisfaction on the dialogue between student and teacher

FACTORS	MEAN	QUALIFYING INTERPRETATION
Providing help	3.80	Satisfied
Dialogue lessens the feeling of distance	3.43	Satisfied
Effect communication throughout the semester	3.42	Satisfied
OVERALL	3.55	Satisfied

As shown in Table 1, the overall mean shows that the students are satisfied in their dialogue between students and teachers. Moreover, as shown in Table 7, the learners are satisfied in all statements under the dialogue between students and teachers. The function of instructors in the teaching and learning of students is crucial. There are areas when students seek clarification from their teachers (Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020; Morin, 2020). According to Table 7, students were happy with their professors since they assisted them with any issues they had and gave them thorough instructions (Taja-on, Miras, and Jurolan, 2021). Students' learning experiences can be improved by instructors who can easily be accessed through messaging applications (Farrell and Brunton, 2021).

Figure 7

Overview of the thematic chart on the experience of the students on the dialogue between student and teacher

Figure 7 displays the overview of the experiences of the students on the dialogue between student and teacher and the percentage of the main themes. The major themes were recorded: accommodating to students (52.42%), productive (17.10%), difficult (18.21%), and unsatisfied with learning (4.83%). Several students stated they have no experience (3.72%) and some gave no response (3.72%). For every theme, the sub-themes were also recorded. Through these responses, the researchers have a baseline data for students' experience with the exchange between the students and their instructors.

Frame 6 listed the main themes and sub-themes of students' experience on the dialogue between student and teacher. Examples of the verbatim responses of the students were extracted to support the themes and sub-themes listed.

Frame 6

Summary of the qualitative themes on the experience of the students on the dialogue between student and teacher

THEMES	SUB-THEMES	EXAMPLE
Accommodating to Students	Responsive	"...I have questions that were responded..."
	Accessible	"...communication online works for me"
	Approachable	"they are approachable if I ask question."
	Considerate	"our teachers understand if we cannot join class and give special activity"
Productive	Informative	"give us needed information to help learning"
	Efficient	"I have good communication between them"
	Helpful	"when we need someone to help us to understand."
Difficult	Anxious	"Being nervous and ashamed..."
	Challenging	"it's challenging to learn by doing."
Unsatisfied with Learning		"...its not clear because of bad connection"
No Experience		"No dialogue at all..."

NOTE: Responses are copied verbatim

Theme 1 and 2: *Accommodating to Students and Productive.* The first theme has four sub-themes, namely responsive, accessible, approachable, and considerate. The second theme has three sub-themes, namely informative, efficient, and helpful. Student were satisfied with their exchanges with their instructors. Some of the instructors were very approachable and responsive to the queries of the students. The exchange of the students and instructors were productive and helped the students improve on their academic performance and clarified their questions about their learning materials and lessons (Farrell and Brunton, 2021; Khattry and Yousef, 2021; Taja-on, Miras, and Jurolan, 2021; Zhang et al., 2020).

Theme 3 and 4: *Difficult and Unsatisfied with Learning.* The third theme has two sub-themes, namely anxious and challenging. Due to the challenge with contacting their instructors, some students find it difficult and makes them anxious making them unsatisfied with their learning experience (Barrot, Llanares, and del Rosario, 2021; Taja-on, Miras, and Jurolan, 2021; Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020).

As presented in Table 7, the students were satisfied in all the parameters under the dialogue between student and teacher. The dialogue is important for the students to be able to ask for

clarification regarding their performance and status in class. Student have stated that the encounter was helpful and productive and their instructors were accessible and responsive to their queries as shown in Frame 6 under the theme on accommodating to students and productive. The students are satisfied with the factor in dialogue between student and teacher.

Online Learning Satisfaction Under Timeliness of Feedback of Undergraduates

Table 8 shows the mean score with qualitative interpretation in satisfaction to online learning concerning the students experience on the timeliness of feedback and presents the degree of satisfaction of the students' regarding the timeliness of feedback.

Table 8

Students' satisfaction on the timeliness of feedback

FACTORS	MEAN	QUALIFYING INTERPRETATION
Efficiency in accomplishing learning task	4.06	Satisfied
Improving on doing learning task	3.75	Satisfied
Improving focus on learning task	3.67	Satisfied
OVERALL	3.82	Satisfied

As shown in Table 1, the students are satisfied in the overall timeliness of feedback. Moreover, as shown in Table 8, the learners are satisfied in all statements under the timeliness of feedback. Furthermore, feedback is important for students in order to help them understand and know their performance and status in their classes (Taja-on and Miras, 2021). The length of time that the feedback could reach to the students would depend on the type of performance being evaluated, but it will help the students improve their performance in class and even know their lapses regarding their submissions (Ranadewa et al., 2021; Morin, 2020).

Figure 8

Overview of the thematic chart on the experience of the student on the timeliness of feedback

Figure 8 displays the overview of the experiences of the students on the timeliness of feedback and the percentage of the main themes. The major themes were recorded: contented with the timeliness of feedback (68.03%) and unsatisfied with the timeliness of feedback (15.24%). Several

students stated they have no experience (5.21%) and some gave no response (11.52%). For every theme, the sub-themes were also recorded. Through these responses, the researchers have a baseline data for students’ experience on the aptness of the feedback given to them by their instructors.

Frame 7 listed the main themes and sub-themes of students’ experience on the timeliness of feedback. Examples of the verbatim responses of the students were extracted to support the themes and sub-themes listed.

Frame 7

Summary of the qualitative themes on the experience of the students on the timeliness of feedback

THEMES	SUB-THEMES	EXAMPLE
Contented with the Timeliness of Feedback	Effective	“Feedback are well disseminated.”
	Swift	“Respond immediately if not busy”
	Satisfactory	“I feel contented for what I got:
Unsatisfied with the Feedback	Difficult for Offline Students	“Hard for offline classes.”
	Late Feedback	“we rarely get feedbacks & if we do, it’s late.”
	Takes a Couple of Days	“taking too long (2 days)”
	Unaddressed	“...it’s not addressed because of unseen messages”
No Experience		“nothing”

NOTE: Responses are copied verbatim

Theme 1: *Contented with the timeliness of feedback.* The theme has three sub-themes, namely effective, swift, and satisfactory. Students were satisfied with the timeliness of the feedback that were provided by their instructors. Some students have stated that the timeliness was effective and swift for many of them (Ranadewa et al., 2021; Taja-on and Miras, 2021; Brooks, Grajek, and Lang, 2020).

Theme 2: *Unsatisfied with the Feedback.* The theme has four sub-themes, namely difficult for offline students, late, takes a couple of days, and unaddressed. Some students have stated that they were unsatisfied because it is difficult for those who opted for modular and blended learning. Some have stated that it takes a couple of days to reach them and some were unaddressed (Taja-on and Miras, 2021; Morin, 2020).

As presented in Table 8, the students were satisfied in all the parameters under timeliness of feedback. The students have stated that they were contented with feedbacks that were given to them and the fast provisions of the teachers with regards to their performance, as shown in Frame 7 under the sub-themes of satisfactory and swift. Contrary, some students have stated that they were not contented with the length of time that they receive their feedback and some of their concerns often go unaddressed as shown in Frame 7 under the sub-themes of late, takes a couple of days, and Unaddressed. But overall, the students are satisfied with the timeliness of feedback.

Online Learning Satisfaction Under Effectiveness of Feedback of Undergraduates

Table 9 shows the mean score with qualitative interpretation in satisfaction to online learning concerning the students experience on the effectiveness of feedback and presents the degree of satisfaction of the students' regarding the effectiveness of feedback.

Table 9
Students' satisfaction on the effectiveness of feedback

FACTORS	MEAN	QUALIFYING INTERPRETATION
Sufficient explanation	3.64	Satisfied
Corrections to incorrect problems	3.57	Satisfied
Clarification to questions raised	3.55	Satisfied
OVERALL	3.59	Satisfied

As shown in Table 1, the student is satisfied overall in their effectiveness of feedback. Moreover, as shown in Table 9, the learners are satisfied in all statements under the effectiveness of feedback. For students to grasp and recognize their performance and position in their classes, feedback is crucial (Taja-on and Miras, 2021). The amount of time it takes for students to receive feedback will depend on the sort of performance being assessed, but it will help them improve in class and even identify any weaknesses with their submissions (Ranadewa et al., 2021; Morin, 2020).

Figure 9
Overview of the thematic chart on the experience of the student on the effectiveness of feedback

Figure 9 displays the overview of the experiences of the students on the effectiveness of feedback and the percentage of the main themes. The major themes were recorded: constructive (42.75%), contented with the feedback provided (31.97%), personally challenging (7.81%), and unsatisfied with the experience (7.81%). Several students stated that they had not experience being provided feedback (5.21%) and a few gave no response (4.09%). For every theme, the sub-themes were also recorded. Through these responses, the researchers have a baseline data for students' experience on the effects of the feedback that were given to them.

Frame 8 listed the main themes and sub-themes of students' experience on the effectiveness of feedback. Examples of the verbatim responses of the students were extracted to support the themes and sub-themes listed.

Frame 8

Summary of the qualitative themes on the experience of the students on the effectiveness of feedback

THEMES	SUB-THEMES	EXAMPLE
Constructive	For improvement	"Students will know what areas to improve."
	Significant	"...the teacher gives feedback to help improve learning..."
	Helpful	"it motivate me and be aware of my performance"
	Meaningful	"I feel amazed that I get some good feedback."
Contented with the Feedback Provided	Satisfactory	"I'm very satisfied getting response from them."
	Thankful	"I really appreciate the efforts of our teachers"
	Approachable	"...they are easy to approach."
	Effective	"Feedback is one of the most effective ways of teaching."
	Responsive	"...they respond on time and easy to approach"
Personally Challenging	Communicating	"It's not as effective as I though due to barriers."
	Contacting	"Sometimes its hard to communicate & understand"
	Anxious	"sometimes i feel anxious when i think about the feedback"
	Problem Coping	"...is hard to be able to cope with it."
Unsatisfied with the Experience	Overwhelming	"Feedback makes me overwhelmed"
	Unsatisfied	"Sometimes the teachers cannot cater the students"
	Unresponsive	"sometimes they don't respond..."
No Experience		"I never received any feedback"

NOTE: Responses are copied verbatim

Theme 1 and 2: *Constructive and Contented with the Feedback Provided.* The first theme has four sub-themes, namely for improvement, significant, helpful, and meaningful. The second theme has five sub-themes, namely satisfactory, thankful, approachable, effective, and responsive. Students were satisfied with the feedback that they have received and stated that these helps them to improve themselves. The feedback was significant and meaningful for many of the students (Ranadewa et al., 2021; Taja-on and Miras, 2021; Brooks, Grajek, and Lang, 2020).

Theme 3 and 4: *Personally Challenging and Unsatisfied with the Experience.* The third theme has five sub-themes, namely communicating, contacting, anxious, problem coping, and

overwhelming. The fourth theme has two sub-themes, namely unsatisfied and unresponsive. Some students find it challenging when they receive their feedback as they feel anxious about their performance and some have problems coping because of the overwhelming feeling. Some students feel unsatisfied due to some teachers being unresponsive to some of the students' queries (Taja-on and Miras, 2021; Morin, 2020).

As presented in Table 9, the students are satisfied in all the parameters under the effectiveness of feedback. The students have stated that the feedback given to them were enough and they were able to understand the feedback given as shown in Frame 8 under the theme of constructive. Additionally, the students were happy with their feedback as it can help them improve their performance in class and comply properly in the next submission as shown in Frame 8 under the theme of Contented with the feedback provided. But some students have expressed that the feedbacks they received were challenging and they had difficulty coping as reflected in Frame 8 under the theme of personally challenging. Over all the students are satisfied with the factor on effectiveness of feedback.

SUMMARY

The study assessed the online learning satisfaction of the students at San Isidro College during the first semester of Academic Year 2021-2022. The learners were satisfied in all eight factors of online learning satisfaction. Generally, the learners were satisfied with their online learning experience. The factor on learning device revealed that the students use their devices to access learning resources online gaining a positive experience for most. However, some students have challenges in using their learning devices because of its availability, like internet connection and confusing use of some applications.

The factor of online discussion and online learning revealed some positive and negative experience of students during their online discussions along with some technical problems. The factor on learning community revealed that the students have a supportive and academic relationship with their classmates along with some negative and uncomfortable interactions. The factor of instructors' characteristics revealed that the students found their instructors to be professional, accommodating, and willing to make compromise. However, some experienced unfavorable experiences with their instructor. The factor regarding the dialogue between student and teacher revealed that the exchange was accommodating and productive, but some found it difficult and were unsatisfied with the exchanges.

The factor on timeliness of feedback revealed that the students were contented with the timeliness of feedback, while others were unsatisfied. The factor on the effectiveness of feedback revealed that the students found it constructive and were contented with the feedback given, while others found it personally challenging and were unsatisfied with the feedback. Among the eight factors the timeliness of feedback was the factor that the students were most satisfied while the instructors' characteristics ranked lowest among the eight factors.

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